

Mixed Chelate Complexes of Iron(III) Containing Dithiocarbamate and Acetylacetonate, Oxinate or Glycinate

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Six compounds of the types $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{AA}')$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{AA}')_2$, were isolated by reacting iron(III) salt with sodium salt of diethyl-dithiocarbamic acid (Nadtc) and acetylacetonate/8-hydroxyquinoline/glycine (AA') in stoichiometric ratio. The compounds were characterized on the basis of their analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared, ultraviolet spectral data and molecular weight measurement. All the compounds were found to be six-coordinated with presumably distorted octahedral configurations.

SYNTHESIS and characterization of a number of mixed chelate complexes of manganese(II and III)^{1,2}, cadmium(II) and nickel(II)³, and copper(II)⁴ have been reported from this laboratory. Keppert⁵ has predicted that the normal geometries of the compounds experience distortion as the 'bite' of the bidentate ligands changes. With this back-ground, the preference of co-ordination number and nature of co-ordination by bidentate ligands such as diethyl-dithiocarbamate(dtc), acetylacetonate(acac), oxinate(ox) and glycinate(gly) around iron(III) is reported in the present communication.

Preparation of complexes :

Preparation of $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{acac})$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{ox})$: Ethanolic solution of ferric chloride, sodium salt of diethyldithiocarbamate and acetylacetonate/oxine were reacted in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio. Alcoholic solution of sodium acetate was added to it till the compounds separated out which were filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{acac})_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{ox})_2$: These compounds were obtained by the same method as above by reacting FeCl_3 , Nadtc and acacH/oxH in 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio.

Preparation of $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{gly})$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{gly})_2$: To an ethanolic solution of ferric chloride was added a mixture of ethanolic solution of sodium salt of diethyldithiocarbamate and aqueous solution of glycine in stoichiometric ratio. The compounds separated out on stirring which were filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Analyses of iron and sulphur by standard methods were consistent with the formulations of the compounds. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol mulls on SP-200 and Perkin Elmer spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded on SP-500 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by a Gouy balance using

$\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated by using Pascal's constants⁶. The conductance measurements were carried out in $\sim 10^{-3} M$ nitrobenzene solution using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter 303. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by Rast method using camphor as solvent. The relevant analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of the compounds are given in Table 1 and infrared spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The low values of molar conductance ($\sim 2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) in nitrobenzene medium (Table 1) indicate that the compounds are non-electrolytes. The high-spin iron(III) ($S=5/2$) with $3d^5$ configuration is expected to exhibit magnetic moment of 5.92 B.M. which should be temperature independent, as the ground term is ${}^6A_{1g}$. On the other hand, the low-spin iron(III) with ${}^3T_{2g}$ term, which is dependent on temperature, is expected to exhibit magnetic moment slightly higher than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. but less than ~ 2.5 B.M. The reported experimental values of magnetic moment of iron(III) for both ${}^6A_{1g}$ and ${}^3T_{2g}$ terms generally respond to the theoretical values. But the dithiocarbamate complexes of iron(III) were found to exhibit magnetic moment values intermediate between spin-free and spin-paired configurations^{6,7}. Three compounds under present investigation viz., $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{ox})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{ox})_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{gly})$ were found to exhibit magnetic moment values of 6.07, 5.93 and 6.07 B.M. as expected for ${}^6A_{1g}$ term. The other three compounds viz., $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})_2(\text{acac})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{acac})_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{dtc})(\text{gly})_2$ were found to exhibit magnetic moment values (3.28-4.09 B.M., Table 1) intermediate between the spin-free and spin-paired configuration as suggested by Figgis and Lewis⁸. Of course, polynuclear complexes were also found to exhibit similar abnormal magnetic moment values.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF MIXED CHELATE COMPLEXES OF IRON(III)

Complexes (Colour)	m.p. °C	%Fe Found (Calcd.)	%S Found (Calcd.)	%O Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Δ_m (mhos)
1. Fe(dtc) ₂ (acac) (dark brown)	260	12.09 (12.87)	24.88 (28.41)	17.90 (18.60)	4.50 (4.69)	3.68	2.0
2. Fe(dtc)(acac) ₂ (brown)	255	12.90 (13.88)	16.10 (15.94)	32.60 (32.80)	5.91 (6.01)	4.09	1.0
3. Fe(dtc) ₂ (ox) (black)	238	11.29 (11.25)	22.21 (25.88)	25.92 (26.58)	5.66 (5.88)	6.07	2.0
4. Fe(dtc)(ox) ₂ (grey)	263	11.77 (11.34)	12.92 (13.02)	45.52 (46.29)	5.25 (5.73)	5.93	2.0
5. Fe(dtc) ₂ (gly) (dark brown)	263	13.09 (13.09)	29.53 (30.07)	11.02 (11.25)	8.59 (9.06)	6.07	1.9
6. Fe(dtc)(gly) ₂ (blackish brown)	268	15.63 (15.85)	18.72 (18.20)	16.83 (17.05)	7.05 (7.25)	3.28	1.8

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF MIXED CHELATE COMPLEXES OF IRON(III)

	dtc			acac		ox	gly		$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$
	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu_s(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{O}-\text{O})$	$\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu_{as}(\text{COO}^-)$	
Fe(dtc) ₂ (acac)	1495 vs	995 s	710 s	1600 vs	1540 s	—	—	—	—
Fe(dtc)(acac) ₂	1495 s	995 s	720 vs	1630 m	1540 w	—	—	—	—
Fe(dtc) ₂ (ox)	1505 s	1025 s	735 w	—	—	1100 vs	—	—	—
Fe(dtc)(ox) ₂	1510 s	1005 s	720 s	—	—	1105 vs	—	—	—
Fe(dtc) ₂ (gly)	1500 w	1000 w	720 s	—	—	—	1375 w	1665 w	3350 w
Fe(dtc)(gly) ₂	1500 w	990 w	715 s	—	—	—	1370 w	1665 w	3350 w

s = sharp, vs = very sharp, w = weak, m = medium.

But the molecular weight measurements of the complexes (not given in the Table) indicate that they are monomers. Mitchell and Parker¹⁰ have suggested that the most plausible explanation of such magnetic properties is the presence of iron(III) in spin state $S=3/2$, because the low magnetic moment cannot be explained by interactions between the iron atoms and must therefore be due to a change of spin state of iron. The most acceptable spin state in such a case is $S=3/2$ (spin-only moment 3.87 B.M.).

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectral bands of the complexes with their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. The ligand dithiocarbamate was known to behave as a bidentate or a monodentate one. The former exhibits $\nu_{as}(\text{C}-\text{S})$ near 1000 cm^{-1} as a single band whereas the latter shows a doublet in the same region¹¹. Also, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the former (above 1485 cm^{-1}) is higher than that of the latter (below 1485 cm^{-1})¹². In the present case, the $\nu_{as}(\text{C}-\text{S})$ band at $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2) was obtained as a single band and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ band was found above 1485 cm^{-1} (Table 2) in all the compounds indicating that diethyl dithiocarbamate is co-ordinated to iron(III) as uninegative bidentate ligand in each case. Infrared spectra of acetylacetonato complexes have been studied extensively. The ligand acetylacetonone can co-ordinate either as uninegative bidentate through its enol form, neutral bidentate through the keto form, or neutral monodentate through carbon atom. In the case of enol form co-ordination, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$

bands are found at 1577 and 1529 cm^{-1} , respectively^{13,14} whereas the strong band due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is obtained near 1700 cm^{-1} when it is co-ordinated through keto form¹⁵. It was found¹⁶ that for carbon bonded complexes, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ were higher and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ were lower than those of the oxygen bonded compounds. In the two acetylacetonato chelates of iron(III), the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ band was found at 1600 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ at 1540 cm^{-1} (Table 2) indicating that the ligand was co-ordinated to the metal atom as an uninegative bidentate one. Similar observations were also reported by Graddon¹⁷. Charles *et al*¹⁸ have reported that in case of oxinate complexes of metals, the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ was obtained at 1120 cm^{-1} region, the position of the band slightly varying with the metal. In the present case, the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ band due to oxine was found at 1100 and 1105 cm^{-1} (Table 2) indicating the co-ordination of the ligand through nitrogen and oxygen atoms as uninegative bidentate one. The $\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$, $\nu_{as}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$ bands due to the ligand glycine, observed at ~ 1370 , 1665 and 3350 cm^{-1} respectively, indicate that it is co-ordinated to the metal atom as an uninegative bidentate one. It has been found¹⁹ that in the case of bidentate nature the glycine group absorbs at 1643 cm^{-1} , unlike either the ionised monodentate group (1610 cm^{-1}) or the unionised monodentate group (1710 cm^{-1}).

The studies of electronic spectra of the complexes are consistent with the octahedral nature of the compounds. The bands obtained at ~ 14700 , ~ 19600 and $\sim 23000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the

transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, respectively as suggested by Ballhausen²⁰ and Balt *et al*²¹. Also as suggested by Kepert⁵, the regular octahedral stereochemistry would experience distortion due to the presence of chelating agents that too of a dissimilar nature. Hence, it is concluded that the six compounds reported here are mixed chelate complexes of iron(III) possessing distorted octahedral geometry.

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